

THE ESSENCE OF TEACHING BASED ON THE COMPETENCE APPROACH TO THE HIGHER EDUCATION PROCESS

Mukhtoralieva Mukhtasar

Assistant of Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute

Rakhmonov Shokhrukh

Student of Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute

Ganiev Avazbek

Student of Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute

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Abstract. *In this article, it is explained that the management of the quality of education in the educational process begins with the identification of the necessary competencies for the acquisition of learning outcomes. Competency approach ensures the quality of education in the modern education system. Competency approach serves to increase the activity of students. The activity of the pedagogue is important in this.*

Keywords: *Competency approach, competence, competence, instrumental, interpersonal, systematic, communication.*

СУТЬ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТНОГО ПОДХОДА К ПРОЦЕССУ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье поясняется, что управление качеством образования в образовательном процессе начинается с выявления необходимых компетенций для приобретения результатов обучения. Компетентностный подход обеспечивает качество образования в современной системе образования. Компетентностный подход служит повышению активности студентов. Важна в этом деятельность педагога.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентностный подход, компетентность, компетенция, инструментальный, межличностный, системный, коммуникативный.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, pedagogues working in the educational system are required not only to restore their acquired knowledge, but also to have a creative approach to solving professional issues, the ability to constantly learn independently, and continuous development of their personal and professional qualities. The ability of professional and creative self-development is considered one of the most necessary qualities for every specialist, including modern pedagogues. Future pedagogues need to develop these qualities in higher education institutions [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Accordingly, the pedagogue is required to have the following professional qualities: look at the student sincerely and with interest; to be ready to accept positive (constructive) criticism from colleagues and students, to make changes to their work accordingly, to have their own personal point of view on the events and social situations in the world around them and to exchange opinions about them with students, to refrain from playing the role of a treasure of knowledge and intelligence aspiration, to respond calmly to sarcastic criticisms directed at one's address, to have a unique position and teaching style in teaching, to have sides that are different from others, to share one's thoughts and feelings with students, to behave competently, to be personally responsible for the result, to be curious, be able to argue etc., demonstrate engagement with their subject and use clear, understandable and expressive language. The basic

and special competencies of the pedagogue play a big role in this. The basic competence of a pedagogue in educational institutions is considered common for pedagogical personnel working in these educational institutions. Special competences are distinguished by the content of the educational process organized by the teacher and the role they play in the development of a well-rounded person. The basic competence of the teacher serves as a basis for the formation of special competences in them. The above-mentioned two types of pedagogical competences are closely related to each other. Therefore, a complex approach to the process of formation of these competencies is required [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The idea of self-development in the educational process is gaining importance today. In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan are to be determined, to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities, to raise the process of training to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education, to advance educational technologies. based on the development of social and economic sectors, improvement of the quality of the educational process in higher education institutions is envisaged.

Currently, ways of determining the essence of self-development are being developed, means of increasing the efficiency of personal and professional self-development of the future pedagogue are being determined.

Pedagogical observations show that there are conflicting situations regarding self-development of students. Today, in higher education, there is a conflict between the need to train pedagogical personnel capable of continuous self-development and the low level of self-development of students. Of course, this conflicting situation shows the need to reveal the factors and pedagogical conditions that influence the effective formation of self-development competence in students in the conditions of the pedagogical training cluster, first of all, the essence of the concepts of "self-development competence" and "developmental education" [1.2].

General competencies can be divided into the following groups in terms of content:

1. Instrumental competence - the ability to know, understand ideas and use them, imagination, methodological skills, understanding of the environment, efficient use of time, computer and information management skills, communication skills.
2. Interpersonal competence - ability to express one's feelings and relationships, critical thinking, social skills, ability to work in a team.
3. Systemic competence - includes the ability to interact with each other as a part of the whole, to assess the position of each component in the system, to plan changes in advance to improve the system, and to design a new system.

The unique feature of education based on the competence approach is that it is a means of bringing a person to a certain level of skill, ability or competence by providing them with systematic, temporary, formal, relevant knowledge, skills and qualifications, the main goal of which is to prepare a person for life, including work (profession). That's why education for sustainable development is a means of bringing a person to a certain level of competence in the stages of systematic education. Most of the developed countries hire college, bachelor, master, doctor of science graduates not based on their diploma or their code in the professional classification, but based on their level of competence.

What do we mean by competency approach?

According to scientific pedagogical and psychological sources, competence is a very complex, multi-part concept common to many disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different in terms of size, content, meaning and logic. The essence of the term also means such concepts as "efficiency", "adaptability", "achievement", "effectiveness", "teachability", "ability" [11.].

In the competence approach, attention is paid not to the educational process, but to its result, to the change of the role of the pedagogue in education, and thus to the change of the methods of organizing education and evaluating its results. In addition, the competence approach implies strengthening the practical orientation of education. Given the importance of acquired knowledge, more emphasis is placed on their practical use. In this approach, the content of education is changed, the development of its personal capabilities is envisaged, for example: learning to read, that is, problems in the field of educational activity, including determining the purpose of cognitive activity, the necessary source of information, finding optimal ways to achieve the set goal, evaluating the obtained results, organizing one's own activities are taught to solve problems in cooperation with other learners [13].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the competence approach ensures the quality of education in the modern education system. In fact, the management of the quality of education begins with the identification of necessary competencies to be mastered as learning outcomes in the educational process. The competence approach serves to increase the activity of students. In order to increase the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to choose educational materials and educational technologies suitable for its goals and tasks. Only then will the students' basic and subject-related competencies be effectively formed. In this process, the pedagogue must regularly enrich his professional knowledge and be armed with information and pedagogical technologies.

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